

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Cerebrospinal fluid proteomic associations of APOE genotypes reveal distinct protective and risk mechanisms for Alzheimer's disease

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Abstract

BACKGROUND: The apolipoprotein E (APOE) gene includes the strongest protective ($\epsilon 2$) and risk ($\epsilon 4$) variants for sporadic Alzheimer's disease (AD), but underlying mechanisms remain unclear. We studied APOE genotype effects on the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) proteome.

METHODS: Using untargeted tandem mass tag mass spectrometry, we analyzed CSF from 227 cognitively normal (CN) controls (A-T-), 165 CN A+, and 177 individuals with mild cognitive impairment (MCI A+) from two large cohorts. We compared

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protein levels across *APOE* genotypes using linear regression and characterized biological pathways.

RESULTS: Five hundred forty-nine of 978 proteins (56%) differed between $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 3$ ($n = 32$ individuals) or $\epsilon 4$ carriers ($n = 181$ individuals) and $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ controls. $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 3$ controls showed the most differences, with higher levels of 280 proteins enriched for neuronal plasticity. $\epsilon 4$ carrier controls showed increased proteins linked to blood–brain barrier dysfunction, and $A+$ $\epsilon 4$ carriers were related to glucose metabolism.

DISCUSSION: Combining two cohorts enabled analysis of the rare *APOE* $\epsilon 2$ genotype, suggesting protective effects may occur through improved neuronal plasticity.

KEYWORDS

Alzheimer's disease, apolipoprotein E, cerebrospinal fluid, cognitively normal, mild cognitive impairment, protection, proteomics, risk

Highlights

- Apolipoprotein E (*APOE*) genotypes show distinct cerebrospinal fluid proteomic mechanisms in early Alzheimer's disease (AD).
- Combining cohorts enabled analysis of rare *APOE* $\epsilon 2$ -associated protection in AD.
- The rare $\epsilon 2$ genotype may confer protection through improved neuronal plasticity.
- *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ carriers show increased blood–brain barrier dysfunction and glucose metabolism.
- These findings offer new insights into genotype-specific mechanisms in early AD.

1 | BACKGROUND

The apolipoprotein E (*APOE*) gene is the major genetic risk and protective factor for Alzheimer's disease (AD).^{1,2} This gene has three alleles: $\epsilon 2$, $\epsilon 3$, and $\epsilon 4$, of which, compared to homozygous $\epsilon 3$ individuals, the $\epsilon 4$ allele increases AD dementia risk ≈ 3 -fold for individuals carrying one $\epsilon 4$ allele to > 14 -fold for individuals carrying two $\epsilon 4$ alleles.¹ Furthermore, $\epsilon 4$ decreases the age of disease onset.^{1,3} In contrast, the $\epsilon 2$ allele is protective: $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 3$ carriers have a 1.5- to 3-fold reduced risk, and $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 2$ carriers have a 2.5- to 7.5-fold reduced risk compared to $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ individuals.^{1,4,5} Note, however, that these protective genotypes are relatively rare, with $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 3$ occurring in roughly 10% to 15% and $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 2$ in only 0.2% to 1.4% of the general population.^{4–7} *APOE* has been implicated in numerous pathways that contribute to AD pathology, including amyloid metabolism and clearance pathways,⁸ synaptic plasticity, lipid and glucose metabolism, and neuroinflammation.⁹ Yet, the precise molecular processes through which different *APOE* alleles affect AD pathophysiology in patients remain largely unknown, while such information may provide more insight into treatments that may help reduce risk for AD.

One approach to studying ongoing biological processes in the brain is through cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) proteomic analyses. One of the first CSF proteomic studies investigating *APOE* effects included 243 targeted proteins in 193 subjects who had abnormal amyloid and reported altered CSF levels of proteins associated with *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ that

were involved in neuronal injury, cell adhesion, and inflammatory processes. These *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ -related protein changes were dependent on clinical stage.¹⁰ Furthermore, another group reported, in part of the same data, decreases in immune-related protein levels with $\epsilon 4$ dose, suggesting that higher $\epsilon 4$ dose aggravates involved processes, but this study did not take into account clinical stage.¹¹ It remains unclear to what extent those results generalize to other cohorts and if additional processes may be detected when increasing the number of proteins studied. Furthermore, the mechanisms through which the *APOE* $\epsilon 2$ allele may contribute to protection against AD remain unclear, as research into this question is restricted by its low prevalence, especially in AD populations.^{4,12} Most knowledge on $\epsilon 2$ -related mechanisms is based on animal or cell studies, the results of which suggest that protective mechanisms may be related to a more efficient amyloid clearance, altered lipid metabolism, and neurotrophic effects to maintain synaptic functioning.^{5,13–15} New proteomic techniques now enable detection of thousands of proteins in the CSF, offering detailed studies into molecular mechanisms related to *APOE* genotypes. It could be hypothesized that these mechanisms of amyloid clearance, lipid metabolism, and synaptic functioning may be reflected in *APOE* genotype-related alterations. While $\epsilon 4$ is enriched in AD populations, the low prevalence of $\epsilon 2$ requires very large sample sizes, on the other hand, to study potential protective effects, but such large-scale CSF studies are rare.

RESEARCH IN CONTEXT

- 1. Systematic review:** The authors reviewed relevant literature using traditional sources (e.g., PubMed) to examine how apolipoprotein E (APOE) genotype influences Alzheimer's disease (AD) pathophysiology through cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) proteomics. While $\epsilon 4$ -related risk mechanisms have been studied extensively, knowledge on $\epsilon 2$ -related protective pathways in patients remains limited due to its low population frequency.
- 2. Interpretation:** By combining CSF proteomics data from two cohorts, we were able to create a large enough sample size to study biological pathways related to the rare APOE $\epsilon 2$ allele in patients. The results suggest that potential protective effects may be mediated through processes related to neuronal plasticity. These findings provide new insights into genotype-specific mechanisms in early AD.
- 3. Future directions:** Longitudinal studies with repeated CSF sampling are needed to examine how these proteomic profiles evolve over time and relate to amyloid and tau pathology to test whether these pathways contribute to protection or risk.

In this study, we took advantage of such approaches that were applied in two large-scale cohorts: the clinical Amsterdam Dementia Cohort (ADC)¹⁶ and the multi-center European Medical Information Framework-AD Multimodal Biomarker Discovery study (EMIF-AD MBD),¹⁷ which, by pooling these together, enabled us to create a sample size large enough to study the potential mechanisms through which $\epsilon 2$ may protect against disease. We further studied early AD alterations reflected in CSF in both cognitively normal (CN) and mild cognitively impaired (MCI) participants.

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS**2.1 | Participants and cohorts**

We selected participants from the clinical ADC¹⁶ and from the multi-center EMIF-AD MBD¹⁷ with CSF proteomic measurements available. In total, we included 165 CN A+ individuals (i.e., cognitively normal or subjective cognitive decline and at least abnormal CSF amyloid; $n = 98$ ADC, $n = 67$ EMIF-AD MBD), 177 individuals with MCI A+ (i.e., MCI and at least abnormal CSF amyloid; $n = 97$ ADC, $n = 80$ EMIF-AD MBD), and 227 CN individuals with normal CSF AD biomarkers (i.e., controls; $n = 166$ ADC, $n = 61$ EMIF-AD MBD). Controls with APOE $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ ($n = 143$) were used as reference group for the main analysis. Diagnosis of MCI was based on international criteria.^{18–20} These studies were approved by local medical ethical committees.

2.2 | APOE analysis

APOE genotyping was performed in blood using the QIAxcel DNA Fast Analysis kit (Qiagen) in ADC,²¹ and in EMIF-AD MBD it was assessed using genome-wide single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) genotyping²² based on the combination of the SNP determining the APOE $\epsilon 4$ allele (rs429358) and the SNP determining the APOE $\epsilon 2$ allele (rs7412). For our main analysis we excluded all individuals with APOE $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 4$ and MCI A+ individuals with APOE $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 3$ because of the small group sizes ($n \leq 6$, but we report descriptive values in Table S1 in supporting information for completeness). For our secondary analysis, we coded APOE genotype as a continuous variable to reflect increasing degrees of genetic risk as follows: $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 3$ as -1 , $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ as 0 , both $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 4$ and $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 4$ as 1 —as these show similar genetic risk for AD⁴—and $\epsilon 4/\epsilon 4$ as 2 .

2.3 | CSF analysis

Lumbar puncture was performed to collect CSF in polypropylene tubes, preferably using a small-gauge atraumatic needle, and processed according to international criteria.^{23,24} In ADC, concentrations of amyloid beta (A β) 1–42 (A β 42), phosphorylated tau 181 (p-tau), and total tau (t-tau) were determined using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA; INNOTEST β -AMYLOID,^{1–42} PHOSPHO-TAU[181P], and HTAU-AG; Fujirebio) as described previously.²⁵ Amyloid abnormality was defined by using a drift-corrected cutoff of < 813 pg/mL.²⁶ In EMIF-AD MBD, study centers used different methodologies to determine biomarker concentrations. Center-specific cutoffs for amyloid were previously established using unbiased Gaussian mixture modeling.²⁷

In both cohorts, proteomics was performed with tandem mass tag mass spectrometry (TMT-MS), in ADC with 16-plexing and in EMIF-AD MBD with 10+1 plexing, both using a high pH reverse phase high-performance liquid chromatography for peptide prefractionation. Reference channels were used to normalize peptide relative abundances between TMT experiments, according to standard procedures.²⁸ Further details regarding CSF sample preparation and MS analysis have been described previously.^{27,29} For both cohorts, protein concentrations were first log-transformed and subsequently scaled according to the mean and standard deviation values of the control group (defined as A–T– individuals with APOE $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ genotype) to aid comparisons between proteins and cohorts. We selected proteins for the present study when they were detected in both cohorts and at least 70% of individuals had observations, resulting in 978 proteins. To increase subgroup sample sizes for different APOE alleles, we pooled data from the cohorts. Prior to pooling, we assessed the comparability of the cohorts by examining the distribution and effect size of key protein SMOC1 between controls versus MCI A+. We observed large and comparable effect sizes in both cohorts, indicating that the effects were consistent across datasets. Finally, to reduce the potential influence of outliers on our results in our secondary analysis, we applied winsorization to adjust outlying values (i.e., below the first quartile $-1.5 \times$ interquartile range [IQR] and higher than the third quartile $+1.5 \times$ IQR) to those

limits. Proteins were annotated to specific brain cell types based on the RNAseq Barres database.³⁰

2.4 | Statistical analysis

Clinical characteristics were compared between APOE groups with chi-squared tests, *t* tests, and one-way analysis of variance where applicable. For our main analysis, we compared CSF protein levels for each APOE genotype to APOE $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ controls, separately for CN A+ and MCI A+, with linear regression models. We performed additional sensitivity analysis to understand potential influence of disease stage on results by comparing CN A+ $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 3$ and $\epsilon 4$ groups to CN A+ $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$, and MCI A+ $\epsilon 4$ groups to MCI A+ $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$. We also repeated analyses taking APOE genotype as a continuous variable to increase power to detect linear effects. All analyses were adjusted for age, sex, and cohort. All proteins were analyzed in separate models. Statistical analyses were performed with R version 4.2.1—"Funny-looking Kid" in R studio.³¹

2.5 | Pathway enrichment analyses

We performed biological pathway enrichment analyses on proteins that were associated with each APOE genotype with the Gene Ontology (GO) database, as accessed with PANTHER (version 17.0),^{32,33} and with Elsevier Pathway Collection, as accessed with Enrichr.^{34,35} We used a liberal significance threshold for proteins to ensure that if multiple APOE-associated proteins would be involved in a similar processes that the enrichment analysis would pick this up. We further restricted analyses to a minimum of 10 proteins and used false discovery rate (FDR) adjustment for multiple testing for pathway enrichment *p* values. Enrichment analyses were performed separately for each set of proteins associated with a specific APOE genotype in a specific clinical stage and separately for protein levels that were increased versus decreased compared to the $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ control group and with the $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ group in their own cognitive group. We further annotated proteins as indicative of blood-brain barrier (BBB) dysfunction according to Dayon et al.,³⁶ who identified proteins with altered CSF/plasma ratios that were strongly related to the CSF/plasma ratio of albumin as a measure for BBB integrity. As our study only includes CSF measurements, we used their protein list as a proxy to identify potential markers of BBB dysfunction detectable in CSF alone.

3 | RESULTS

3.1 | Cohort demographics

In total, 227 CN controls, consisting of 21 $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 3$ (9.3%), 143 $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ (63%), 6 $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 4$ (2.6%), 53 $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 4$ (23.3%), and 4 $\epsilon 4/\epsilon 4$ individuals (1.8%); 165 CN A+ individuals with 11 $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 3$ (6.7%), 49 $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ (29.7%), 4 $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 4$ (2.4%), 79 $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 4$ (47.9%), and 22 $\epsilon 4/\epsilon 4$ (13.3%); and 177 MCI A+ individuals, including 4 $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 3$ (2.3%), 48 $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ (27.1%), 2 $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 4$ (1.1%), 82 $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 4$

(46.3%), and 41 $\epsilon 4/\epsilon 4$ (23.2%), were included (Table S1 describes characteristics for all groups). Due to the limited sample size, we excluded all individuals with APOE $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 4$ and MCI A+ individuals with APOE $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 3$ in the main analyses. Table 1 describes the clinical characteristics of the APOE genotypes included in the main analysis.

Briefly, A+ individuals were older compared to controls. The distribution of APOE genotypes in A+ groups conformed to expectations based on genetic risk, with more $\epsilon 2$ carriers in the amyloid-negative control group and more $\epsilon 4$ carriers in CN A+ and MCI A+ groups. The proportion of women was somewhat higher in CN A+ compared to controls and MCI A+. MCI A+ had the highest tau levels, whereas controls had the lowest. Furthermore, individuals with more $\epsilon 4$ alleles tended to be younger than individuals without $\epsilon 4$, and in MCI A+, individuals with more $\epsilon 4$ alleles had higher tau levels than individuals without $\epsilon 4$ (Table 1). In the following analyses we compared protein levels in each APOE genotype across clinical stages to $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ controls and to $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ individuals in their own clinical stage. In total, 549/978 (56%) proteins showed differences in one or more APOE genotype subgroups compared to our $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ control group (Figure 1). Below, we further describe the results separately for $\epsilon 2$ and $\epsilon 4$ compared to $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ controls and compared to $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ individuals in each clinical group. Detailed results can be found in Tables S2–S5 in supporting information.

3.2 | Potential mechanisms underlying protective effects of the APOE $\epsilon 2$ allele

We tested CSF proteomic alterations in $\epsilon 2$ controls against $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ controls to study which mechanisms may be related to $\epsilon 2$. Of all groups tested, CN A- $\epsilon 2$ carriers had the largest number of proteins with altered levels in CSF, in total 320 (33%), compared to $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ controls (Figure 1, Table S2). Most of these proteins (280/320) had increased CSF levels and were enriched for processes related to synaptic plasticity, such as nervous system development (PFDR 4.63E-30), axonogenesis (PFDR 1.43E-15, term = 2), synapse organization (PFDR 1.80E-06), and regulation of the ERK1 and ERK2 cascade (PFDR 1.79E-03), and included proteins such as NRCAM, NPTX1, NPTXR, BDNF, CNTN1, EPHA4, and ROBO1 (Figure 2, Table S4). Many of these proteins were associated with neuronal expression (Figure S1 in supporting information). The proteins in this group were further enriched for the "Eat me signal: apoptotic cell initiates phagocytosis" (PFDR 0.002; AXL, TYRO3, CALR, MFGE8, ADGRB1; Table S5) and contained other specific proteins involved in protein degradation, such as RNF13 and BLMH. The 40 proteins with lower CSF levels in $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 3$ controls were associated with processes such as coagulation (PFDR 4.39E-06), complement activation (PFDR 4.33E-05), and the humoral immune response (PFDR 3.75E-04), including proteins such as SERPIN-family members, APOH, F9, C8G, C8B, C8A, CFI, CFB, VTN, and AHSG (Figure 3, Table S4). These proteins were enriched for BBB function (23 out of 73 BBB proteins, *p* value < 0.001). While previous studies indicated higher levels of these proteins are associated with BBB dysfunction,^{27,29} we observe in this $\epsilon 2$ group lower levels of these proteins.

TABLE 1 Demographics according to APOE genotype and clinical stage for main analyses.

	CNA-T- controls			CNA+			MCI A+		
	ε2/ε3	ε3/ε3	ε3/ε4	ε4/ε4	ε3/ε3	ε3/ε4	ε3/ε3	ε3/ε4	ε4/ε4
N	21	143	53	4	49	79	22	82	41
Age	59.6 [8.8]	62.7 [7.6]	59.9 [7.5]	59.5 [5.5]	67.8 [8.4]	66.6 [8.2]	65.1 [7.8]	68.3 [7.4]	65.8 [5.8]
Sex (female)	11 (52)	65 (46)	17 (32)	1 (25)	30 (61)	43 (54)	12 (55)	42 (51)	16 (39)
Total tau (Z score)	0.66 [0.1, 1.2]	0.02 [-0.5, 0.5]	0.13 [-0.5, 0.6]	-0.66 [-1.2, 0.3]	0.98 [-0.5, 3.1]**	1.28 [0.1, 2.4]***	0.97 [0, 2.2]**	2.18 [1.9, 6.2]***##	3.10 [2.5, 4.8]***#
AT profile									
A-T-	21 (100)	143 (100)	53 (100)	4 (100)	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
A+T-	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	29 (63)	47 (67)	15 (68)	22 (27)	5 (12)
A+T+	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	17 (37)	23 (33)	7 (32)	60 (73)	36 (88)

Note: Results presented in mean [SD] or n (%). All individuals with APOE ε2/ε4 and MCI A+ individuals with APOE ε2/ε3 are excluded from the main analysis and table because of the small group sizes (n ≤ 6).

Abbreviations: APOE, apolipoprotein E; AT, amyloid and tau; CN, cognitively normal; MCI, mild cognitive impairment; n, number; SD, standard deviation.

Compared to APOE ε3/ε3 controls:

*p value < 0.05,

**p value < 0.01,

***p value < 0.001.

Compared to APOE ε3/ε3 in same clinical group:

p value < 0.1,

p value < 0.01,

p value < 0.001.

FIGURE 1 Heatmap of CSF protein levels in each group, compared to ε3/ε3 controls. Red shades indicate higher protein levels, and blue shades indicate lower protein levels compared to controls. CN, cognitively normal; CSF, cerebrospinal fluid; MCI, mild cognitive impairment.

In our combined sample, there were still 11 CN A+ individuals with the ε2/ε3 genotype. Exploratory analysis in this group indicated that compared to ε3/ε3 controls, 79 proteins had higher CSF levels, and these proteins were associated with glucose metabolism (PFDR 4.46E-07, e.g., PKM, TPI1, GOT1, MDH2, PGAM1, PGK1, ENO1, ENO2, GADPH; Figure 2). For 72 proteins the CSF levels were lower than ε3/ε3 controls, which overlapped with proteins decreased in ε2/ε3 controls (22/40; 55%), and were related to BBB function (44 out of 73 BBB proteins, p value < 0.001), complement activation (PFDR 6.62E-29), coagulation (PFDR 3.33E-19), and humoral immune response (PFDR 6.86E-22; Figure 3, Table S4). Repeating analyses comparing ε2/ε3 CN A+ to ε3/ε3 CN A+ indicated overlap of 34/79 proteins (43%) with increased levels and 39/72 (54%) with lower levels. Specifically, proteins with lower levels in ε2/ε3 CN A+ compared to ε3/ε3 CN A+ were similarly enriched for complement activation (PFDR 1.35E-19), coagulation (PFDR 9.46E-12), and humoral immune response (PFDR 1.51E-19), indicating that these

may be indeed APOE ε2 specific, rather than related to amyloid pathology.

3.3 | Pre-amyloid changes in controls carrying the APOE ε4 allele

Next, we investigated if pre-amyloid-related alterations could be observed in controls with one or two APOE ε4 alleles ($n = 57$). Compared to ε3/ε3 controls, we observed higher levels of 16 and lower levels of 3 proteins in APOE ε3/ε4 carriers ($n = 53$). Increased proteins were associated with BBB impairment (4 out of 73 BBB proteins, $P = 0.03$; C2, CP, C1RL, and SERPINA5) and complement activation (PFDR = 0.04, including IGLV7-46 and IGHA1; Table S2). Most protein effects tended to become stronger with the increasing number of ε4 alleles within controls (Table S3). Including control ε4/ε4 carriers ($n = 4$) in the analysis therefore resulted in more significant increased proteins

Upregulated in APOE genotypes

FIGURE 2 Main GO pathways of proteins upregulated in different APOE genotypes across clinical syndromes versus ε3/ε3 controls. From left to right: ε2/ε3 controls, ε2/ε3 CN A+, ε3/ε4 CN A+, ε4/ε4 CN A+, ε3/ε3 MCI A+, ε3/ε4 MCI A+, and ε4/ε4 MCI A+. APOE, apolipoprotein E; CN, cognitively normal; GO, Gene Ontology; MCI, mild cognitive impairment.

Downregulated in APOE genotypes

FIGURE 3 Main GO pathways of proteins downregulated in different APOE genotypes across clinical syndromes versus ε3/ε3 controls. From left to right: ε2/ε3 controls, ε2/ε3 CN A+, and ε3/ε4 CN A+. APOE, apolipoprotein E; CN, cognitively normal; GO, Gene Ontology.

(n = 23) and BBB protein involvement (F2 and AMBP, 6 out of 73 BBB proteins p value = 0.02). These processes may reflect early effects of ε4, potentially upstream from amyloid aggregation.

3.4 | APOE ε4-related proteome changes in CN A+ and MCI A+

We next investigated APOE ε4-related changes in CSF protein levels in amyloid-positive individuals and tested if these alterations depended on clinical stage (i.e., CN A+ vs. MCI A+). All A+ ε4 carrier groups

had higher levels of proteins (such as PGAM1, GOT1, PKM, PGK1, ENO1, ENO2, ALDOC, and GAPDH) that were enriched for glucose metabolism (PFDR range 2.35E-08 to 6.68E-04; Figure 2), and to a lesser extent this effect was also observed in amyloid-positive ε3/ε3 carriers (Table S4). This effect became stronger in MCI A+ compared to CN A+, and within MCI A+ this effect also tended to become stronger with increasing number of ε4 alleles (PGAM1, PGK1, PKM, ALDOA, GAPDH; Table S3). We further observed higher levels with ε4 genotype in oxidative stress-related proteins (e.g., PARK7, PPIA, SOD1, SOD2), which seemed to coincide with these changes in glucose metabolism. Furthermore, in ε3/ε4 CN A+ individuals we observed 36 proteins with

lower levels than $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ controls that were associated with lipid remodeling (PFDR = 0.02) and cholesterol transport (PFDR = 0.005, including e.g., CETP, PON1, APOC1, PLTP; Figure 3, Table S4). Repeating analyses comparing $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 4$ and $\epsilon 4/\epsilon 4$ APOE genotypes to $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ individuals within CN A+ and MCI A+ indicated that 12 proteins with lower levels in CN A+ $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 4$ were associated with lipid-related processes and cholesterol transport, similarly compared to controls. Comparing $\epsilon 4/\epsilon 4$ MCI A+ individuals to $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ MCI A+ indicated that 22 proteins with higher levels were related to metabolic processes (GO pathway PFDR range = 0.039 to 0.055; Table S4).

3.5 | Comparing APOE-related proteome changes across disease stages to autosomal dominant AD and Down syndrome AD

Finally, we made a heatmap (Figure 4) for a selection of proteins that have previously been reported to be altered in the natural history of autosomal dominant AD (ADAD)³⁷ and in Down syndrome AD (DSAD)³⁸ to understand how APOE-related changes in pre-dementia stage of sporadic AD compare to those previous studies. Figure 4 indicates that SMOC1 was most elevated in A+ individuals with both intact cognition and MCI regardless of APOE genotype, which seems consistent with early effects reported in ADAD and DSAD. However, while in ADAD SMOC1 elevations were closely related to decreasing A β in the disease course, we did not observe increased SMOC1 levels in APOE $\epsilon 4$ A-. Furthermore, we observed that SPON1, which had high levels in ADAD and DSAD in very early amyloid aggregation stages, was only elevated in A+ $\epsilon 4$ carriers in all stages, but not in A+ $\epsilon 4$ non-carriers. We found proteins related to synapse changes, glucose metabolism, and stress response (e.g., YWHAZ, PKM, YWHAG, ENO1, ALDOA, and PGAM1) that were increased early in ADAD and DSAD and were also elevated in all A+ CN individuals, regardless of APOE genotype. While this effect became stronger in MCI A+ compared to CN A+ in $\epsilon 4$ carriers, in non-carriers the effects were strongest in the CN A+, suggesting a different timing of processes associated with these proteins depending on APOE genotype. This seems to be different from the timings of alterations observed in ADAD, in which some of the metabolism-related proteins (LDHB, GOT1, PEBP1, TPI1, GMFB) were observed to have transient pre-dementia increases, and others (YWHAZ, PKM, YWHAG, ENO1, PGAM1) remain elevated post-dementia. In DSAD, by contrast, some of these proteins (ENO1, PEBP1, LDHB, TPI1) were reduced before dementia onset, while others rose much closer to or even post dementia onset. Furthermore, we compared a group of proteins related to synaptic and neurosecretory processes (SCG2, VGF, NPTX2, NPTXR, THY1, MFGE8). While these proteins are decreased after ADAD or before DSAD dementia onset, consistent with synaptic and neuronal loss, we observed elevation of these proteins in our $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 3$ CN A- carriers. Finally, we observed that several proteins related to metabolism (PKM, LDHB, GOT1, PEBP1, GMFB, MDH1) that were increased in ADAD and DSAD were also increased in our CN A- $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 3$ carriers, which was unexpected as these individuals are least likely to develop AD.

4 | DISCUSSION

In this study we investigated the effects of APOE genotype on the CSF proteome in individuals with normal cognition and normal CSF amyloid and tau, and in individuals with abnormal amyloid without dementia. While the APOE gene includes both the strongest risk and protective factors for sporadic AD, little is known about the underlying mechanisms through which these genotypes exert their effects, in particular because only 10% to 15% of the population carries the protective $\epsilon 2$ genotype.^{5,6} By leveraging two large cohorts, we assembled a large enough sample to study this question, using a CSF proteomic approach to probe molecular processes in great detail. We observed the most pronounced effects of APOE $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 3$ controls compared to $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ controls, with protein alterations pointing toward involvement of synaptic plasticity-related processes, the eat-me-signal, and BBB integrity. On the other hand, $\epsilon 4$ carrier controls had CSF protein changes indicative of BBB dysfunction, suggesting that BBB alterations may occur upstream in terms of both protective and risk effects of APOE genotype. Furthermore, we observed that protein levels associated with APOE $\epsilon 4$ in CN A+ and MCI A+ individuals were associated with glucose metabolism, oxidative stress, and lipid remodeling, suggesting that APOE $\epsilon 4$ risk may impact these processes downstream from amyloid pathology. In summary, these results indicate that protective mechanisms of $\epsilon 2$ and risk mechanisms of $\epsilon 4$ affect the CSF proteome, involving both similar and distinct processes.

While a great body of literature on APOE exists,^{13,39} few studies so far have investigated associations of APOE genotype in patients through CSF proteomic analysis, and all have focused on $\epsilon 4$ -related effects. Two studies using the Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative (ADNI) dataset investigated APOE effects in AD, which included panels of 200 and 300 targeted proteins.^{10,11} Two recent studies, within ADNI⁴⁰ and the Global Neurodegeneration Proteomics Consortium cohort,⁴¹ used the SomaScan platform (> 6000 proteins) and reported, respectively, 57 and 229 proteins related to APOE $\epsilon 4$ genotype that were related to innate immune activation, inflammation, and indications of BBB dysfunction in APOE $\epsilon 4$ carriers, which we also observe. An ADNI study indicated that APOE $\epsilon 4$ was associated with higher injury marker levels such as tau and neurogranin, which we also observed in the current independent cohort.¹⁰ Also in ADNI, we¹⁰ and others¹¹ reported decreased levels of complement factors and related proteins in $\epsilon 4$ carriers. In this study we replicated some of these findings (e.g., lower levels of KNG1, APCS, and C7 in $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 4$ CN A+), and detected four additional proteins (CP, C1RL, SERPINA5, and AMBP) to be altered in $\epsilon 4$ A- controls, pointing toward early BBB disruption. As these proteins were not measured in previous ADNI studies, our untargeted approach might provide insight into potential pre-amyloid mechanisms of $\epsilon 4$. Furthermore, in contrast to previous findings, we observed increased levels of other proteins (C2 and F2) associated with the complement pathway already in $\epsilon 4$ carrier controls. Possibly, differences in cohort composition (individuals in our study were \approx 10 years younger compared to ADNI), size, and methodological variations (we used untargeted TMT-based proteomics, while ADNI

FIGURE 4 Protein changes stratified by amyloid status, *APOE* genotype, and clinical stage, revealing how molecular changes track the trajectory of sporadic AD, allowing for comparison to autosomal dominant AD and Down syndrome-associated AD.^{37,38,46} AD, Alzheimer's disease; *APOE*, apolipoprotein E; CN, cognitively normal; MCI, mild cognitive impairment.

relied on targeted mass spectroscopy) may explain these diverging findings.

Another new finding from our study was that because we could pool two large cohorts, we were able to investigate the effect of $\epsilon 2$ on the CSF proteome. As the $\epsilon 2$ allele is only present in 10% to 15% of the population,⁵ our large cohort allowed for unique analysis into the protective biological effects of $\epsilon 2$. In these analyses, we found a large-scale proteomic signature related to $\epsilon 2$ carrier controls in which proteins had higher levels than in $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ controls and were enriched for neuronal plasticity-related processes. This suggests that possibly one mechanism through which *APOE* $\epsilon 2$ exerts protection against AD may be through neuronal connectivity. Previous animal studies have described a neurotrophic effect of $\epsilon 2$, which helps to preserve neurons and synaptic functions.¹³ Our $\epsilon 2$ controls further

had higher levels of proteins associated with protein degradation and the "eat-me" signal, which is expressed on cells or particles to promote phagocytosis and clearance of, for example, apoptotic cells, which is important for maintaining tissue homeostasis.⁴² Possibly, this may reflect a mechanism through which clearance may be enhanced. Furthermore, we found that proteins of which higher CSF levels have previously been related to (loss of) BBB integrity^{27,29,36} were lower in $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 3$ controls as well as $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 3$ CN A+ individuals. Possibly, the notion that these same proteins were lower than controls in $\epsilon 2$ may indicate that this genotype also influences BBB integrity, possibly reflecting protective effects. However, large longitudinal studies mapping how amyloid and tau pathology develops in $\epsilon 2$ are necessary to test whether these pathways truly confer protection or risk upstream from amyloid aggregation.

Furthermore, we observed that complement-related proteins had elevated CSF levels already in control $\epsilon 4$ carriers. Perhaps we could only now detect this effect due to the larger sample size in this study ($n = 57$ $\epsilon 4$ carrier controls, compared to $n = 8$ in previous studies). Amyloid plaques trigger complement activation,⁴³ and *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ has been shown to enhance this activation.⁴⁴ Possibly we observe a response to very early amyloid-related changes in our $\epsilon 4$ carrier controls. Longitudinal studies with repeated CSF measurements are necessary to further investigate this question. Furthermore, we observed downregulation of proteins involved in lipid metabolism in A+ $\epsilon 4$ carriers, both compared to controls and $\epsilon 3/\epsilon 3$ CN A+ individuals, suggesting a highly specific *APOE*-related mechanism. *APOE*'s role in lipid transport is well known, and both impaired lipid transport and poor lipidation in $\epsilon 4$ carriers may further exacerbate *APOE*-related detrimental processes (e.g., less efficient amyloid clearance, decreased neurotrophic functioning) in AD.⁹ A previous experimental study in mice reported that microglia activation in the presence of amyloid aggregation differed in *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ lipoprotein composition compared to $\epsilon 3$, resulting in restricted surrounding of microglia around plaques and reduced $A\beta$ uptake.⁴⁵ It would be of interest to further investigate the *APOE* genotype with a combined proteomics and lipidomics study in CSF in patients.

Finally, we used our stratification by amyloid status, *APOE* genotype, and clinical diagnosis as a cross-sectional approximation for disease trajectories, comparing *APOE*-related proteins in sporadic AD to those reported in ADAD and DSAD.^{37,38,46} In those studies, SMOC1 was elevated very early, and we similarly found increased SMOC1 as the strongest effect of A+ across all groups, supporting robust early involvement in amyloid aggregation independent of *APOE*. SPON1, an extracellular matrix protein elevated early in ADAD and DSAD, was increased only in *APOE* A+ $\epsilon 4$ carriers, suggesting a genotype-dependent effect. Notably, a subset of metabolic and synaptic integrity proteins, reported to be altered in ADAD and DSAD, were also increased in our CN A- $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 3$ carriers, suggesting these may also underlie processes of resilience. Future research is needed to understand whether this signature indeed contributes to reduced cognitive decline.

Some limitations have to be noted about this study. First, although our overall group size was large because we combined two cohorts, the number of individuals with rare *APOE* genotypes remained relatively small, especially $\epsilon 2$ A+ MCI individuals (reflecting its protective effects) and homozygous $\epsilon 4$ controls (reflecting its risk effects). Therefore, we were unable to specifically study these subgroups, and we aim to increase our sample sizes for future research. This also limited our ability to further subdivide groups into different amyloid and tau biomarker subgroups. Still, using tau as a continuous outcome, *APOE* $\epsilon 4$ genotype was associated with higher t-tau levels, particularly in later clinical stages. Larger studies are needed to further investigate if *APOE* genotypes in combination with amyloid and tau biomarker profiles may be related to specific proteomic signatures. Second, CSF proteomics do not directly reveal the anatomical origin of proteomic alterations, leaving it unclear whether CSF proteomic concentrations may reflect better global or regional BBB integrity in $\epsilon 2/\epsilon 3$ individuals. Imaging approaches such as arterial spin

labelling perfusion magnetic resonance imaging are required to spatially map BBB integrity, and studies within the Developing BBB-ASL as a Non-Invasive Early Biomarker (DEBBIE) consortium are currently addressing this.⁴⁷ In addition, new experimental BBB models, such as induced pluripotent stem cell-derived systems with different *APOE* genotypes, may provide complementary mechanistic insights into the genotype-specific CSF protein changes. Third, our analyses were cross-sectional, and so the differences between clinical stages we observed require further verification with longitudinal proteomic data to understand how processes change with disease progression. Finally, while our findings may point toward processes that could play a role in disease pathogenesis through CSF proteomics, functional follow-up studies are necessary to further study mechanisms. A strength of our study was the large overall sample size, enabling us to characterize CSF proteomic alterations related to $\epsilon 2$, which has not been studied before in such detail in humans. In addition, the use of untargeted proteomics allowed for identifying biological processes associated with *APOE* genotype in A+ individuals and controls, which were not captured in previous CSF proteomic studies using a targeted approach.

In conclusion, we completed one of the largest studies investigating effects of *APOE* genotype on the CSF proteome in older individuals with and without AD pathology, which provides novel insights into the protective mechanisms of *APOE* $\epsilon 2$ and risk mechanisms of *APOE* $\epsilon 4$.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

J.P. received consultation and speaker honoraria from Nestle Institute of Health Sciences, Innovation Campus, EPFL, Lausanne, Switzerland; Ono Pharma, Schwabe Pharma Switzerland; OM Pharma Switzerland; Roche Pharma; and Fujirebio Europe, all not related to this work. H.Z. has served on scientific advisory boards and/or as a consultant for AbbVie, Acumen, Alector, Alzinova, ALZPath, Annexon, Apel-

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has received honoraria for a workshop on grant writing organized by Stiftung Synapsis, Alzheimer Forschung Schweiz AFS (payment to university), and is a member of the executive board of EADC. P.J.V. and B.M.T. have a patent on AD subtypes (PCT/NL2020/050216). The remaining authors report no conflicts of interest. Author disclosures are available in the [supporting information](#).

CONSENT STATEMENT AND ETHICS APPROVAL

Written informed consent was obtained from all participants or surrogates. The medical ethics committees at each study site approved the studies.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

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